

AMERICAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND INNOVATION (AJMRI)

ISSN: 2158-8155 (ONLINE), 2832-4854 (PRINT)

VOLUME 2 ISSUE 2 (2023)

PUBLISHED BY
E-PALLI PUBLISHERS, DELAWARE, USA

Knowledge, Acceptance and Readiness to the K-12 Program Among Technical-Vocational Teachers

James A Benaning^{1*}

Article Information

Received: March 12, 2023

Accepted: April 07, 2023

Published: April 10, 2023

Keywords

*K-12 Acceptance, K-12 Awareness,
K-12 Readiness, Philippines,
Preparedness, Technical-Vocational
Program, Technical-Vocational
Schools, Technical-Vocational
Teachers*

ABSTRACT

The study sought the preparedness among technical-vocational teachers towards the K-12 Program implementation. This descriptive-correlation study determined the level of knowledge, acceptance and readiness to the K-12 program implementation among technical-vocational high school teachers. There were 63 respondents included using the stratified random sampling. The study intends to seek answers towards the level of knowledge, acceptance and readiness of the respondent before the implementation of the K-12 Program. Findings served as the bases for intervention scheme through an orientation plan for the recommended programs. There is a very high level of knowledge, high level of acceptance and readiness among technical-vocational high school teachers towards the K-12 Program. There is no significant relationship between the level of knowledge and the level of readiness and no significant relationship between the level of knowledge and the level of readiness and level of acceptance and level of readiness towards the K-12 Program implementation among the respondents. The technical-vocational high school teachers of the Division of Davao City, possessed, practiced, and are prepared to implement the K-12 Program under R.A.10157 and have strengthened the program. The proposed intervention scheme through an orientation plan as programs for technical-vocational high school teachers training after thorough study should be implemented, monitored and evaluated by both the respective school heads, division education supervisor on technical-vocational program education of the Division of Davao City, Philippines.

INTRODUCTION

Readiness of trade schools state the prompt availability of generation resources towards the delivery of its quality educational services and skills development tasks stipulated in the manual of its standard operating procedures in the aspect of human resources, curriculum, technical key competencies, financial resources and student services while preparedness state the full readiness for action in the aspect of school facilities, teacher preparations, instructional leadership, school services, school programs and projects, barangay capability building initiatives and community linkages among stakeholders in a school-based management system.

The government is confronted with a big step forward for the K-12 challenge of overcoming its main obstacles in the financing of education most specially the underfunded requirement of the tech-voc. schools for the skills training of the senior high school program notwithstanding the prevailing insufficient readiness and preparedness among tech-voc. schools as mandated in their manual of operations. The continuous need to closely monitor and assess the preparations made by these schools and their stakeholders as it progresses is highly measurable and inevitable.

Trade schools offer instruction in skilled trades in the different areas of specialization with at most one to two years of training in the technical or vocational courses to acquire a Certificate of Competency (COC)/National Certification Level I-II (NC I-II) upon completion. It aims to produce world class quality skilled graduates

that meets the demand for blue collar jobs as oppose to profession graduates that cater to white collar jobs.

The respondent schools are ought to assess its preparedness for the K-12 Program Implementation the needed gap of resources for sufficiency or insufficiency thereof the mandated requirement as public tech-voc. high school stipulated in its manual of operations based from the findings of the study in terms of technical key competencies, student services, school facilities, teacher preparation, and instruction. To improve the quality of skills education that public tech-voc. high schools ought to give their students they deserve, then at least it might be better for administrators and teachers to look further into their field and reflect on considerable measures of assessing their school's current status towards readiness and preparedness for the K-12 Program implementation. The anticipated findings of the study will provide the necessary action and orientation plan that would prepare the respondents schools towards the implementation of the K-12 Program. Professionally, the researcher would like to measure his state of readiness-towards the full implementation of the K-12 as a newly-trained NC II teacher certified by TESDA from a public tech-voc. high school here in Davao City division and how prepared he is for the K-12 implementation. It is for the following premise that the researcher is prompted to conduct the study. It is but inevitable that due to these background reasons there is a need to measure the state of readiness and preparedness among public technical-vocational high schools in Davao City division. Data gathered by the

¹ Department of Education, Philippines

* Corresponding author's e-mail: jabenaning@gmail.com

indicators of the study may provide a pool of knowledge on resource shortages among the respondent trade schools as the frontier of skills training for the incoming senior high school students due to the implementation of the K-12 Program of the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 [R.A No. 10533].

LITERATURE REVIEW

This study is anchored on the Manual of Operations for Public Technical-Vocational High Schools which provide for over-all guidance and policy directions in the efficient and effective implementation of the “Strengthened Technical and Vocational Education Program (STVEP)” to be strictly adhered to by all Technical and Vocational Public Secondary Schools across the country (DepEd ORDER No. 89, s. 2010) (2012, June 29), the legal mandate through RA 7796 otherwise known as the TESDA Act which was signed into law on August 25, 1994 giving the Technical Educational Skills Development Authority (TESDA) the full jurisdiction to manage the Philippines Technical-Vocational Education and Training (TVET) for the development of skilled manpower in the country, and currently RA No. 10157 and House Bill No. 6643 which subsequently enacted into law the K-12 Basic Education Program otherwise known as the “Enhance Basic Education Act of 2012” which institutionalize one year of kindergarten into the basic formal system of education and the mandate to implement the additional two years of skills training called as the Senior High School (SHS) in the secondary level of education (2012, October 10 DepEd Press Release). The K-12 curriculum in school will bring back the blue-collar skills training in partnership with TESDA as the national certification agency giving body after the skills training and assessment. Furthermore, Article XIV, Section 3 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution states that the school shall inculcate patriotism and nationalism, foster love of humanity, respect for human rights, appreciation of the role of the national heroes in the historical development of the country, teach the rights and duties of citizenship, strengthen ethical and spiritual values, develop moral character and personal discipline, encourage critical and creative thinking, broader scientific and technological knowledge, and promote vocational efficiency. In fact, the Education Act of 1982 or Batas Pambansa Blg. 232 stipulates the following objectives for the secondary education: 1) Continue the general education started in elementary; 2) Prepare the learners for college; and 3) Prepare the learners for the world of work. Section 3, Title 6 (Education, Culture and Sports), Book IV, Administrative Code of 1987 provides: “Section 3. Powers and Functions. - To accomplish its mandate and objectives, the department shall have the powers and functions of formulating, planning, implementing and coordinating the policies, plans, programs and projects for the following: (1) Elementary, secondary, physical and international education; (2) Non-formal and vocational or technical education; (3) Higher education; (4)

Development of culture; (5) Foreign and locally assisted projects and other activities relative to Subsections (1), (2), (3) and (4); and (6) Perform such other functions as may be provided by law.”

Equally important, the Medium-Term Philippine Development Plan (MTPDP) 2004-2010, states that “the secondary level curriculum shall be revised to complement the adjustment in the revised elementary education curricula. The new curricula shall include the following subjects: (a) integrative science; (b) applied mathematics; (c) communication skills; (d) career/work exposure which includes work ethics, vocation/job counseling and seminars/plant/office visits, trends in the job market in the various trades and professions, job prospecting and application, supervised personal career planning, and entrepreneurial possibilities and skills, including agricultural skills and other life skills not included in the existing values formation curricula.” Philippine Main Education Highway: Towards A Knowledge-Based Economy has included some recommendations on Tech-voc., as follows: a) include DepEd in the harmonization process (on tech-voc. education), b) Tech-Voc. NC1/NC2 in basic education, not just in selected Tech-Voc. high schools (NC3/NC4 for TV1s), c) design more model curricula to expand the coverage of ladderized programs, and d) ensure constancy or education policy despite changes in administration (national/CHED/ TESDA/DepEd).

In addition, the Philippines educational system embraces formal and non-formal education. Currently, the K-12 enactment into law mandated the institutionalization of the one-year kindergarten and two years of senior high school of the enhanced basic formal education reform agenda of the country towards the development of quality graduates for white collar jobs. Non-formal education includes education opportunities outside of formal schooling particularly the development of skills for blue collar jobs. There is an increasing demand for people who have graduated from vocational trades schools. More and more people favor them over four-year degree courses. A lot of large corporations are tapping into the human resources provided by vocational trade schools in an attempt to expand and further specialize their work force. Most businesses today consider hiring employees with vocational training to handle specialized jobs. The Congressional Commission for Education or EDCOM enacted in 1990 by the Congress Joint Resolution No. 2 concluded from the results of review and assessment which paved change towards a trifocalization of the management of the country’s educational system. Basic Education was subsequently changed to Department of Education (DepEd) through the passage of RA 9155 or Governance of Basic Education Act on August 2001.

Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) as legally mandated through RA 7796 otherwise known as the TESDA Act which was signed into law on August 25, 1994. Higher Education involving tertiary education in community colleges, universities,

and specialized colleges became the domain of the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) which was established through the enactment of RA 7722 or Higher Education Act on May 18, 1994. (2005, Syjuco). The TVET in the Philippines provides education and training opportunities to prepare students and other clients for employment which addresses the skills training requirements of those who are already in the labor market and would need to upgrade or develop new competencies to enhance employability and improve productivity.

A report indicates a huge potential clientele for TVET which includes primarily the high school graduates, secondary school leavers, college undergraduates and graduates who want to acquire competencies in the different occupational fields, unemployed persons who are actually looking for work, returning OFW who decided to discontinue working abroad and those who are currently employed wanting to upgrade their skills or acquire new skills. To emphasize, the public TVET providers include the 121 TESDA Technology Institutes composed of 57 schools, 15 Regional Training Centers, 45 Provincial Training Centers and 4 Specialized Training Centers. Other public TVET providers include State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) and local colleges offering non-degree programs; DepEd supervised schools, LGUs, and other government agencies providing skills training programs. The TESDA as the authority in TVET is mandated to provide relevant, accessible, high quality and efficient technical education and skills development in support of the development of high quality Filipino middle level manpower responsive to and in accordance with the Philippine Development goals and priorities which has also a quality policy that states its worth is measured by the satisfaction of the customers served” (2005, Syjuco).

The Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2012 would give access to two more years of free basic education for Filipinos, while enabling holistic development and readiness for different paths. (Education Secretary Br. Armin A. Luistro FSC, October 20, 2012). The K-12 Basic Education Program prescribes an enhanced system that includes one year of kindergarten, 6 years of elementary education, and 6 years of secondary education consisting of 4 years of Junior High School and two years of Senior High School. It aims to develop lifelong learners who will be prepared for higher education, employment, entrepreneurship and equip them with middle-level skills, readiness for higher education, and readiness for livelihood. (Rep. Sandy Ocampo, October 20, 2012). A nationwide survey conducted with 1,200 respondents representing all economic classes, and a balance across genders, age groups, and locale (urban and rural) reveals increasing public approval of K-12 and high confidence in DepEd’s capacity to achieve goals. Among Filipino adults, 72% believe that K-12 will give students more sufficient knowledge and preparation for work and college compared to those who finished 10 years of basic education. The percentage of Filipinos who believe that

more students will be encourage to finish Senior High School (SHS) is 69% because it is equivalent to two years of college. Moreover, 68% believe that more students will finish SHS even with the additional cost and number of years because the K-12 graduates will be better prepared for work, higher education and business. (The Third Quarter 2012 Social Weather Report, October 25, 2012). To address concerns on preparedness “the enhanced curriculum is a product of thorough researches which look into the best practices of our neighbor countries and our experiences in schools and communities nationwide, and that the features of the program and implementation strategies to be employed by Department of Education (DepEd), Commission on Higher Education (CHED), Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA), and necessary support from the House, Senate, Local Government Units, and the Private Sector. (House of Representative Presiding Officer of the Committee on Basic Education and Culture Sandy Ocampo, October 20, 2012).

The K-12 Basic Education Reform Program is a promise of crucial change to enhance together the formal and non-formal system of education in the Philippines which will make it a central strategy that capitalizes on the most important resource of our country by equipping the Filipino People with functional knowledge and lifelong learning skills for livelihood and sustainability attune to the global standards of the 21st century. (Pangulong Benigno S. Aquino III). The DepEd seeks to raise the quality of education to global standards which is believe to be the answer to the lingering problem of the country’s perennially high unemployment rate and dropout rate in schools. To address the problem, DepEd has added two more years to high school. DepEd said that the K-12 program will enable students to land a job after graduation. Under the program, students will be taught new subjects and given vocational and technical training, and on-the-job-training. (DepEd, 2012)

Graduates of secondary tech-voc. schools have to go through assessment by TESDA-certified assessors in order for them to earn a certificate of competency or a National Certification (NC) I or II depending on their skills proficiency. The department provides continuing skills enhancement training and assessment for secondary tech-voc. teachers who are teaching competency-based curriculum in 26 areas of specialization in arts and trades, agriculture and fishery in collaboration with the National Tech-Voc.

Educational Training Trainers Academy (NTTA)-TESDA. This means that an assessor from one school can also be an assessor in other schools as long as he/she is commissioned by TESDA. (Luistro). DepEd’s Strengthened Technical and Vocational Education Program (STVEP) equips high school students with TESDA-certifiable skills to prepare them for the world of work, post-secondary education or entrepreneurial opportunities. “Our goal here is to bring back the dignity of blue-collar jobs by producing highly-skilled workforce

demanded by the community and the industry sector,” said Luistro. STVEP is also aligned with the goals of the k-12 Basic Education Reform Program that aims to produce high school graduates who are prepared for employment or college education. Reforms in education absolutely requires preferential attention as our sacred duty that through a collective efforts as local and national leaders, we can provide every Filipino with the best shot at a decent life giving them high quality education that is accessible to all emphasizing DepEd’s progress in achieving milestones for the education sector especially on augmenting resource shortages. (Ocampo, 2012)

The K-12 Basic Education Program rolled out when Universal Kindergarten was implemented in all public schools in 2011, followed by the enhanced Grades 1 and 7 curriculum beginning school year 2012-2013. In two years, the K-12 program, including the Mother Tongue Based, Multi-Lingual Education Agenda have been efficiently rolled out in phases. Also, the benefits and mechanics of all intended program reforms were effectively communicated and reached as wide as possible all stakeholders and the public in general. (Luistro, 2012). The schools piloting the SHS modeling program will draw much anticipated learning prior to the full implementation of K to 12 in 2016. When implementation is completed in 2018 as mandated, the school year 2018-2019 will mark the beginning of a newly reformed entire basic education system. For the K-12 program, the additional two years will be about specializations giving the students three choices: academic (for those who will be pursuing college), technical-vocational (for those who planning to work as soon as they graduate senior high school) and sports and arts (for those who wants to be in Sports or Arts).

The National Career Assessment Examination assess based upon their choices made as well as the need of the community. To elaborate, within the K-12, a student will only have to finish 12 years in order to get a job which is more practical for parents as they will only have to spend 12 years in education and their child/children can start helping them with the finances. But with the current situation of the education system here in the country, we may not be readily prepared yet for the K-12. Adding two more years will require more classrooms, more teachers

and more teaching materials which are seldom solved problems nationwide. The lack of classrooms has always been a problem of the current education system proven by class shifting or class shortening and multi-grade classes.

There are three major educational problems that besiege the country today. Allocation of budget for the implementation of K-12 should be allotted instead to building of classrooms. Improvement/ increase of the teacher’s benefits and salary to boost the teacher’s morale and to perform their best. Improvement of school facilities such as laboratories and utilities which would augment towards the meaningful learning experience of learners. This means to fix first the basic needs of our education, the basic tools needed for teaching otherwise in a haphazard manner, the schools may not be ready and prepared in the delivery of quality educational services much more than the implementation of the K-12 as mandated. It is noted that literatures used in this study is taken from various sources which has direct relationship to the study in general. Few studies which have direct bearing to the study are included in this literature. Nonetheless, the above theories and literatures serve as basis in the development of the problem, methodology and in the interpretation of the findings. All the theories and literatures that are included in this study will serve as foundation and guide the researcher in the conduct of the study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study employed descriptive-correlational study utilizing both quantitative and qualitative approaches. It is descriptive because it presents and describes the result where it is established by hypothesis and correlational-relational showing the relationship of the concept of the study. Further it also uses qualitative approach in order to further consolidate the result of the study.

Table on Distribution of Respondents per School

There was a total of 63 respondents included in the study using the stratified random sampling. The respondent schools comprising all technical-vocational institutions in the third congressional district of Davao City belonging to the Cluster 9 of the Division of Davao City.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents Per School

School	School Administrators	Vocational Teachers	Related Subject Teachers	Total
Baguio HS of Agriculture	1	5	5	11
Tambobong HS Annex	1	3	3	7
Baguio National School of Arts and Trades	1	9	9	19
Elias P. Dacudao Gumalang School of Home Industries	1	4	4	9
Marilog High School of Agriculture	1	4	4	9
Wangan National High School	1	4	4	9
Total	6	29	29	63

Statistical Treatment

The analysis and interpretation of the research data was facilitated using the following tools: Frequency counts and simple percentage distribution was used to describe the profile of the respondents as well as the respondent’s school profile. Weighted mean was used to determine the level of readiness and preparedness of the respondent school towards the mandated standards of operation for public tech-voc. high schools and the implementation of the Senior High School (SHS) Program of the K-12 Law. Chi-square (c2) test was used to determine that the level of prompt response into actions and preparations made by the respondents to its mandated operational standards in their respective school had made significant as to its readiness and preparedness most especially in the implementation of the Senior High School (SHS) Program of the K-12 Law.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation (Pearson r) was used to find out whether significant relationship exists between the levels of readiness and preparedness of the respondents to standard operating procedures and the Senior High School Program Implementation.

F-test is used to find out whether significant difference exists between the school’s compliance to manual of

operations by prompt actions made towards readiness/ preparedness to the K-12 and the demographic profiles of the respondents. It will compare which statistical models has the best fit from the total population which the data gathered were sampled in which the test statistics has a frequency distribution under the null hypothesis. All statistical computations are done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 16.0 Software. Testing of hypothesis is based at alpha = 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the result of the tabulated data based on the responses taken from the data-gathering instrument. The interpretation and descriptive analyses are discussed as a result of the different statistical applications made use for the study.

Table 2. Summary Table on the Level of Knowledge
 Table 2 presents the summary table on the level of knowledge with an overall mean of 3.24 and interpreted as Very High. This means that majority of tech-voc. teachers in this study are highly equipped with the technical key competencies, provision of student services, school facilities, knowledgeable on what tech-voc. teachers to prepare and its relevant instruction.

Table 2: Summary Table on the Level of Knowledge

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
Technical Key Competencies	3.36	VHL
Student Services	2.92	HL
School Facilities	3.42	VHL
Teacher Preparation	3.26	VHL
Instruction	3.22	VHL
Overall	3.24	VHL

*Legend: Very High Level (VHL) - 3.01-4.00; High Level (HL)- 2.01-3.0; Low Level (LL) - 1.01-2.0
 Very Low Level (VLL) - 0.01-1.00*

On Technical key competencies Table 2 as Appendix H, presents the level of knowledge of the respondents in terms of technical key competencies with a grand mean of 3.36 described as very high. This means that majority of the tech-voc. teachers as the respondents of this study possess the knowledge on its technical key competencies. The Department of Education through the Division of Davao City already has an existing technical-vocational High School. The tech-voc. teachers under this curriculum are equipped with the necessary knowledge under this area from seminars and trainings of this department. The item 7 ‘teachers know that career pathways lead to eligibility for certificate of competency shows a mean value of 3.51 as very high level supports these findings. There is no reason that tech-voc. teachers are not career pathways oriented because these schools are under the tech-voc. curriculum. Upon the implementation of the K-12, these teachers are already in advantage compared to some academic high schools hence they have a very high level of technical key competencies. President Aquino signed the R.A. 10157 otherwise known as the K-12

Law. This law provides the full implementation of the k-12 program by the year 2018. Further, the government doesn’t have difficulties in implementing this program because tech-voc.-teachers are highly knowledgeable on this aspect.

Table 2 as Appendix H, shows the level of knowledge of the respondents in terms of student services with a grand mean of 2.98 as high. This means that majority of the tech-voc. teachers are knowledgeable under this indicator, yet, it does not qualify to a very high level. This means that there are student services which are not provided to them thus, majority of the items are described as High that supports the overall, finding. The item 1 “teachers are aware of giving service to students through the K-12 Law SHS Program pre-orientation and seminars has the lowest mean score. This only shows the importance on the conduct of test and measurement to the students to validate whether technical key competencies are acquired by them. While the latter only shows that there was not enough orientation on SHS program to the students. In order to fully implement the K-12 program, the above

services should be provided to the student otherwise it could defeat the purpose. The teachers should be fully knowledgeable that student services play an important role on the success of the k-12 program.

Table 2 as Appendix H, discloses the level of knowledge of the respondents in terms of school facilities with a grand mean of 3.42 as very high. This only means that majority of the tech-voc. teachers are knowledgeable under this indicator and acknowledged for a fact that facilities especially for tech-voc. schools are indispensable tools towards achieving effective theoretical and practical learning. This means further that adequate provision for tools, materials equipment, competency learning modules, maintenance and installation of physical plants as well as facilities must be provided to them thus, majority of the items are described as Very High that supports the overall, finding.

The item 5, 'the teachers acknowledge the importance of enough chairs, number of NC II teachers per specialization courses, classrooms, library, clinics and school canteen has the highest mean score described as very high and is followed by the item 2 "the teachers are aware of its adequate instructional/learning materials especially CBLM. This only shows the importance of prioritizing immediate concerns to ensure readily available facilities to acquire the skills among the different major courses offered. Functional facilities rationally available for students validate whether technical key competencies are acquired by them. While all the other got very high means that there was no enough school facilities for the SHS program implementation. In order to fully implement the K-12 program, the above facilities should be provided to the student otherwise it could defeat the purpose. The teachers should be fully knowledgeable that sufficient facilities in teaching students the conceptual skills competencies through practical learning play an important role on the success of the K-12 program.

Table 2 as Appendix H, is the presentation on the level of knowledge of the respondents in terms of teacher preparation with a grand value of 3.23 shown as very

high level. This described that majority of the teachers are equipped with the skill on the preparation of instructional teaching materials and other aspect related to the curriculum of the k-12 program. The following items shows the highest values such as the teachers acknowledge the importance of values and behavioral skills necessary to the Senior High School Curriculum, the teachers are highly trained in teaching their major fields of specialization whether vocational or related subject. It only means that tech-voc. teachers are highly trained on this matter. This is the basic knowledge and tool of a teacher otherwise one cannot teach the lesson effectively without it just like a farmer need a plow the field. The students are the seed. Before it grows it need care, attention and fertilizer. In teaching we need all the necessary preparation and requirements especially because the end-product are human being as key players of economic development of the country. The k-12 is designed to meet these demands through the department of education.

Table 2 as Appendix H, demonstrates the level of knowledge of the respondents in terms of its instruction with a grand value of 3.12 or very high. This proves that majority of the teachers possess the necessary skills of instruction with the highest value on the knowledge that technical-vocational schools, the exploratory course are offered in grade -7. This only justify the fact, that the Training acquired by the teachers every summer were still fresh in their minds because the agency conducted training every summer until the completion of the fourth-year high school teacher, after which the addition senior high school are added into the number of years that a Filipino students have for the secondary or high school education.

Further, it is shown on the data, that the teachers have lowest result as to the knowledge of research. Unreported data on this study were there were only 3 teachers who have the master's degree program that which need attention by the agency. (Please see attached appendices A: Instrument of the research)

Table 3: Summary Table on the Level of Acceptance

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
Technical Key Competencies	3.31	VHL
Student Services	3.18	VHL
School Facilities	3.20	VHL
Teacher Preparation	3.38	VHL
Instruction	3.17	VHL
Overall	3.25	VHL

*Legend: Very High Level (VHL) - 3.01-4.00; High Level (HL)- 2.01-3.0; Low Level (LL) - 1.01-2.0
Very Low Level (VLL) - 0.01-1.00*

Table 3 presents the summary table on the level of acceptance with an overall mean of 3.25 as Very High. This means that under this variable and its indicators, tech-voc. teachers under this study only prove of their knowledge of the program and at the same time they have

already their willingness to support the new curriculum. Table 3 as shown on Appendix I, reflects the level of acceptance of the respondents in terms of technical acceptance. The data shows the highest mean values of 3.58, 3.57 and 3.4 went to the technical-vocational teachers

recognize the development of conceptual skills on tech-voc. basic, common and core competencies towards their students and the technical-vocational teachers conform to the teaching of technical key competencies in technical drawing and entrepreneurship as mandatory subjects. The results entail that majority of the tech-voc teachers are technically competent as to the different program offered by the different tech-voc school of the Division of Davao City. On the technical-vocational teachers that implements the standard operating procedures of a technical-vocational school, support staff services follow standard provision for necessary support services and support the implementation of the senior High School Program could have the lowest mean value yet as very high value.

This is only mean that half of the teachers adhere to accepts the different technical key competencies. The researcher strongly believe that it could not be due to the correctness and appropriateness of the contents of the different competencies but it might be due to the administration and implementation of the program. Teaching is laborious. But as a teacher, one does not find this, as a hindrance, but teachers just want to be productive in terms of the learning of the students. Teachers are very conscious that the efforts are not a wastage; when the government may decide to stop the implementation of the program. If this government be able to compete to the world market, it must have to see to it, that the k-12 program must in placed and be given priority, otherwise everything are just only rhetoric and dreams.

The data on the level of acceptance of the respondents in terms of student services is shown on table 3 as Appendix I with a grand value of 3.18 described as very high. This only project that majority of the teachers accept the fact that student services are important factors so that one student can graduate or finish the program and the same time, the k-12 program and the school achieve a high level of performance. The items are willing to provide a Career Guidance Education towards their students obtains the highest mean value of 3.51 described as very high. This means that career guidance orientation is accepted among teachers on the success of the implementation of the program. The government provides an item in all basic education program of a guidance counselor because the government recognizes the role that this particular employee provided for the supervision and implementation of the program.

The item 'conduct technical-vocational course placement test obtain the lowest mean value of 2.79 though describe as high. This result only shows that there are teachers who are not in favor that placement test be conducted. According to Dr. Jean L Bejano, former Education Program Supervisor in TLE at the same time supervised the tech-voc. schools in city, said, that "If placement test is conducted there could maybe shortfall of teachers in a particular program because students tend to enroll a program that they think quite in demand in the market. So that, If the teachers are given the opportunities, they

must have at least to control the number of students as to the required capacity of a particular program for a certain teacher. Generally, the k-12 program is design to help the students and the country to compete with the curriculum of the rest of the world. The students as the clientele of the product must be given top-priorities on top of this public interest should be over personal interest for the good of public service. (R.A. 6713 otherwise known as code of conduct of government officials and employees). Table 3 as shown on Appendix I, exhibits the data on the acceptance of the respondents in terms of school facilities with a grand mean of 3.20 as very high.

This only depicts that infrastructure as hard projects of the government generate results just like government tangible projects provide labor, employment and income. The level of acceptance is quite very high because, it makes teaching comfortable and rewarding. It could be very difficult to teach tech-voc. education under the tree or just anywhere else in the school because it requires instruments, apparatus and entail more practical work than its theoretical aspect of learning. It is clearly shown on the data how chairs, library facilities, clinics, NC 11 teachers affect the overall school performance because of its data gets of 3.68 as very high level; and the item 'the teachers acknowledge the provision of lot area for additional buildings and other school facilities with a mean value of 3.68 and 2.40 described as very high level and high level.

The former would only mean that most of the teachers are facilities oriented and the latter described that teachers don't pay so much attention on whether there is vacant lot or not for further expansion of the school facilities. Although it is true on this aspect, but there are a few teachers recognized that the teachers must accept this value because there are school heads who do not follow school plan and design on its school land use program. The case may be of some school head are not familiar on the land use program. With this kind of orientation of Table 3 reveals the level of acceptance of the respondents in terms of teacher preparation with the grand mean of 3.38 as very high. This indicates that the teachers perceived the effect of teacher preparation in the delivery of the services to the students. Teacher preparation provides the blueprint on what and how to impart the technical and vocational knowledge to the students. One who is prepared is mostly willing to accept what would happen at the end of its journey.

Whether it is good or bad result, what makes it comfortable that one is prepared and therefore willing to take the risk and challenges at the end of it. the course. The teachers are willing to attend training and assessment in the major fields of specialization among tech-voc. Courses got the highest mean value of 3.66 because it is in this venue that teachers acquire knowledge and skill of tech-voc. education vis-a-vis tech-voc. education program. The item, 'the teacher in their tech-voc. specialization course can demonstrate a skill with a competence gets lowest mean value of 3.24. This only means that there

are teachers who are not confident enough to teach tech-voc. education. This finding supports the above findings. Therefore, training and seminars are very essential to meet the demands for quality teachers. In general, the k-12 program is well planned and well prepared. As to technical persons in the field is also technically prepared. Table 3 as shown on Appendix I, on instruction of the level of acceptance of the respondents has a grand mean of 3.17 as very high. It only means the applicability and expertise of the department of education and the TESDA on this area. Instruction as concept refers to the entire curriculum designed embedded in the program. It is shown on the data that the conduct of activities in

preparation of the SHS obtains the highest mean value. It is because that the DepEd continuous training for the k-12 program have been very successful with the financial support of some stake holders in the private sector of the country. Again, on the data regarding acceptance of the teachers on research shows a very lowest score. It only shows that how could a teacher accept the fact that research should be also a priority among teacher when one does not have the skill of research. In general, the level of acceptance of teachers in terms of research is quite very satisfactory and commendable hence, it can predict that the k-12 program in one way or the other could be able to sustain the program.

Table 4: Summary Table on the Level of Readiness

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
Technical Key Competencies	3.02	VHL
Student Services	3.02	VHL
School Facilities	2.92	HL
Teacher Preparation	3.07	VHL
Instruction	2.89	HL
Overall	2.98	VHL

Legend: Very High Level (VHL) - 3.01-4.00; High Level (HL)- 2.01-3.0; Low Level (LL) - 1.01-2.0 Very Low Level (VLL) - 0.01-1.00

Table 4 is the summary table on the level of readiness with an overall mean of 2.98 described as very high. This finding show that tech-voc. teachers are s not only knowledgeable and ready of the k-12 program but they are very ready as well for the full implementation of the new curriculum.

Table 4 as shown on Appendix J, is the Level of readiness of the respondents in terms of technical key competencies with a grand mean of 3.02 as very high. This result shows that majority of the tech-voc. teachers in Davao City possess this indicator. This means that the teachers are ready on this aspect in fact they have been ready since these teachers are tech-voc. teachers. This finding conforms on the table 1 on the knowledge of technical competencies of tech-voc. teachers and on table 2.1 which both show the same result. This means that if a teacher is knowledgeable and accepts the different key competencies would also follow that the teacher is ready to implement the program. It can be noted that the overall mean is closer to high which indicates that almost half of the respondents show that they are not yet ready on the full-implementation of the k-12 program. Also, item 3 and item 6 on readiness of the implementing the standard operating procedures and support staff services show the lowest score though described as high, only indicate that the above result also identify that there are teachers who are not yet ready on the above items. A very high level of readiness on the technical key competencies in the implementation of k-1 program should be maintained among tech-voc. teachers otherwise the entire program is not understood by the teachers and the students as the recipient of the K-12 curriculum.

Table 4 as appended is the Level of readiness of the respondents in terms of student services with a grand mean of 3.02 as very high. As to the readiness of student services, it garnered a grand mean of 3.02 which shows very high. This means that majority of tech-voc teachers are ready on the implementation of the k-12 which is also consistent to the readiness of its technical key competencies of this result and it is also further supported on table 3 on the level of acceptance on student services show the same result though on the level of knowledge shown on table 1.1 which show only high. These finding disclose the importance for the success of the k-12 program.

The item 1 ‘the teachers are ready to conduct pre-orientation seminar towards the K-12 program gets the highest mean value of 3.09 described as very high. This means that respective tech-voc. schools and teachers are very ready to conduct orientation seminar on the K-12 program. The provision on this item is very important because it is through this approach that schools and teachers can fully explained the concept of the K-12 program and the students could fully support the program. As far as the readiness of the teachers to conduct placement test and providing scholarship and job places show a very low score with 2.90 and 2.75 and both described as high. This only means that the k-12 program is not very clear on this area or maybe there is no existing policies and procedures on this matter. Teachers should be given the task to design placement test according to the needs and nature of the students in a particular tech-voc school and at the same time identifying students as to what program they intend to enroll otherwise there could

be no teachers on some subjects or programs. In other words, the success of the K-12 depends on the teachers and its student services.

Table 4 as shown on Appendix J, discloses the level of readiness of the respondents in terms of school facilities with a grand mean of 2.92 described as high. Although it is high, yet, the value is closer to low. This only means that majority of the tech-voc. school in the Division of Davao City are not yet ready for the implementation of the k-12 program. This finding is confirmed by the Department of Education, Division of Davao city Annual Report for Tech-Voc. High school specifically school facilities for SY 2012-2012. Considering that the K-1 program is on its second year of implementation, hence, budget appropriation for school facilities under this agency could probably has no enough amount especially on the construction of additional buildings. Although it is very high on the inspection of the proper installation and maintenance of physical plants and its facilities but it is only up to inspection and survey but, without actual project implementation. However, the teachers got a very low score on the compliance to minimum standard student ratio on the use of different tools and equipment with a mean value 2.57 but described as high. This only shows that school facilities are not enough to cater a number of students in a public tech-voc. high schools. To address this problem, the government provides financial support to private high schools so that public high school students who wants to enroll in private high school who are poor especially deserving students be given the chance of a tech-voc. education. The k-12 program depends on the product of the students it could have. It can be translated when Senior High School graduates could supply the demand of the labor market that can compete to the world market of skilled manpower.

Table 4 as shown on Appendix J, discloses the level of readiness of the respondents in terms of teacher preparation that shows very high. This means that preparation of teachers as to the subject taught, assessment test, books, manuals values education, national certification clearly demonstrate that majority of the teachers are ready on this aspect. Aside from the fact, that the respondents are from existing tech-voc. high school education in the Division of Davao City, the teachers are expected to perform well and he/she can do that when a particular teacher is always prepared before his / her actual teaching. The evidence of the performance of teachers is

shown on his/her PAST. Unsatisfactory performance for 3 consecutive years could be a solid ground of dismissal from the service (Civil Service Manual), thus, the teacher should show performance and one can do it when there is always preparation in his/her teaching. Further, the readiness of teachers on training and assessment supports the findings as very high also on its knowledge and acceptance. It only confirms that a tech-voc. teachers should upgrade and update trainings and acquire national certification, otherwise, a particular tech-voc. teacher is not effective teacher. As to the national certification of tech-voc. teacher obtain the lowest mean value with 2.75, yet describe as high which only means that majority of the tech-voc. teachers are not NC II holder, therefore are not yet ready for the K-12 program. The Readiness of the teacher requires a holistic approach. It does not only mean being physically and psychologically ready. One should have the right ethics and attitudes such as its physical, psychological and its socio-cultural aspect that contribute to a new tech-voc. teachers expected by the government to produce productive students as partners of development especially in the countryside. This is the main goal of the K-12 program.

Table 4 as shown on Appendix J, is the Level of readiness of the respondents in terms of Instruction with a grand value of 2.89 as high level. This means that majority of the teachers are not ready as far instruction is concerned. If the above characters are not yet ready, It can only be deduced that there are no sufficient instructional materials for classroom instruction. The software of the tech-voc. Instructional materials are downloadable only that the school cannot sustain to cover the expenses to produce it to every students. This means that the government should have to augment the budget to the department of education for this program and maybe respective school should find possible ways and means to solve this problem through community linkages who can fund for the production of the materials. Taking into account item 14 on the readiness to teach TLE/TVE courses based on the learning outcomes and performance criteria by the TESDA has the highest mean value. This only indicates the important role of TESDA as to the instruction and curriculum of the K-12 program because tech- voc. education is under their mandates beside the technical and conceptual expertise are from this agency with the direct collaboration of the Department of Education, hence, budget allocation from the government national

Table 5: Relationship Between Level of Knowledge and Level of Acceptance of the Respondents

Variables Correlated	Computed r value	P value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Technical Key Competencies	.136	.798	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Student Service	.735*	.024	Reject Ho	Significant
School Facilities	.181	.771	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Teacher Preparation	.083	.894	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Instruction	.722*	.005	Reject Ho	Significant

*significant at 0.05 level

budget to this agency is a requirement to address this problem

Table 5 shows the significant relationship between the level of knowledge and level of acceptance of the respondents. The result shows an overall interpretation of not significant. “no overall in the table” This means that the knowledge and the acceptance of the k-12 program of the teachers are not related. This only shows that teachers are doubtful on the sustainability of the

curriculum because it is already an experienced among the teachers on the changes of curriculum before the full implementation of the current curriculum used. The student services and instructions have the significant level on knowledge and acceptance of the K-12, because these are the key factors of the said program. The rest of indicators could not be significant but only means less significant because it does not directly play the role on the impact of the k-12 program, hence, null hypothesis

Table 6: Relationship between Level of Knowledge and Level of Readiness of the Respondents

Variables Correlated	Computed r value	P value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Technical Key Competencies	.186	.724	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Student Service	.046	.906	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
School Facilities	-.388	.518	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Teacher Preparation	.307	.616	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Instruction	.667	.827	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

accepted. Table 6 shows the relationship between the level of knowledge and level of readiness of the respondents with an overall interpretation of not significant in the table. This means that the above concepts are not related. A teacher who has the conceptual knowledge does not mean that one has the readiness to implement

the program. There could be other factors to consider such as budget, human resources, administration and others. The indicators mentioned-above though not significant, in terms of its knowledge and readiness, yet, interrelated on its functions, thus, contribute on the implementation and the success of the program. These

Table 7: Relationship Between Level of Acceptance and Level of Readiness of the Respondents

Variables Correlated	Computed r value	P value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Technical Key Competencies	.765*	.045	Reject Ho	Significant
Student Service	.406	.244	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
School Facilities	.553	.333	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Teacher Preparation	.849*	.032	Reject Ho	Significant
Instruction	-.363	.181	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

**significant at 0.05 level*

findings show somewhat similar result and interpretation as indicated on table 1 and table 3, hence, null hypothesis is rejected or accepted. Table 7 depicts the relationship between the level of acceptance and level of readiness of the respondents that show generally not significant. This means that the two variables do not have direct relationship. Both indicators could be independent, yet, in one way or the other, influence the success of the K to 12 program. As to the technical key competencies and teacher preparation with a computed pvalue of .045 and .244 respectively show significant result. This findings only support table 5 and 6 on the relationship of above-mentioned variables, hence, null hypothesis is not rejected or accepted.

CONCLUSION

This study is all about the level of knowledge, acceptance and readiness to the K-12 program of technical-vocational public high schools of Davao City Division. This aims at identifying the level of knowledge, acceptance and readiness with the same variable in all concepts which includes: Technical Key Competencies; Student Services,

School Facilities, Teacher Preparation and Instruction. This study also determine the relationship of knowledge, acceptance and its readiness. Also this study is designed to determine factors that could improve the knowledge, acceptance and readiness of the K-12 program. Majority of the research-respondents who are the public tech-voc. teachers of the Division of Davao City have a very high level on knowledge, acceptance and readiness of the k-12 on Technical Key Competencies; Student Services, School Facilities, Teacher Preparation and Instruction. There is no significant relationship between the level of knowledge and level of acceptance of the respondents. There is no significant relationship between the level of knowledge and level of acceptance of the respondents in terms of technical key competencies, student service, school facilities, teacher preparation and instruction. Relationship between level of knowledge and level of readiness of the respondents. There is no significant relationship between the level of knowledge and level of readiness of the respondents in terms of technical key competencies, student service, school facilities, teacher preparation and instruction.

Relationship between level of acceptance and level of readiness of the respondents. There is no significant relationship between the level of acceptance and level of readiness of the respondents in terms technical key competencies, student service, school facilities, teacher preparation and instruction.

Based on the findings, it is concluded that the public tech-voc. teachers of the Division of Davao City have knowledge, full acceptance and are physically and mentally ready for the full implementation of the K-12 curriculum.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the findings drawn from this study, the following are recommended. The proposed action plan as programs for the tech-voc. education of the secondary department Division of Davao City in cooperation with the DepEd Regional Office-XI and the Technical Education Development Authority of the Region should be studied for further improvement and applicability; The proposed action plan as intervention scheme should be monitored and evaluated which shall be made use for research and for further utilization of the program; There must be a massive and thorough education of teachers of the K-12 program and be integrated as activities of the Human Resources Development down to school level. There must be concrete policies and implementing rules and guidelines as regards to the full implementation of the K-12 program.

Strengthened training and seminars designed to identify best teacher for particular skills instruction towards learners. There must be a feasible plan to sustain the K-12 program. Further, research should be conducted similar to this in order to gather benchmark regarding the K-12 program.

The following studies are highly recommended by the researcher: A study on the full implementation of the K-12 program among tech-voc. schools. Comparative study of the full implementation of the K-12 program in Region XI. Problems encountered on the implementation of the K-12 program among tech-voc. schools in the Davao city Division.

REFERENCES

DepEd Order No. 89, s. (2010). Manual of operations for the technical and vocational public secondary schools
 DepEd Technical-Vocational Education Task Force (2007). Strengthened technical-vocational education program (STVEP) Technical key competencies for tech-voc. secondary schools.
 Declaration of Policy Republic Act. No. 7796 (1995). Technical education and Skills Development Act of 1994 with Implementing Rules and Regulations.
 DepEd Technical-Vocational Education Task Force (2007). Strengthened Technical-Vocational Education. Declaration of Policy. Republic Act. No. 7796 (1995). Technical Education and Skills Development Act of 1994 (with Implementing Rules and Regulations).

DepEd Press Release (2012). Philippines on track for K-12 reform and Zero Backlog in 2013.
 DepEd Press Release (2012). HOR Education Committee Approves Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2012.
 DepEd Press Release (2012). Nationwide Survey Reveals Increasing Public Approval of K-12 and High Confidence in DepEd's Capacity to Achieve Goals.
 DepEd Press Release (2012). More schools to pilot DepEd's Senior HS program.
 Education, Publish (2011). A Primer to the Vocational Trade Schools- What to research on? Program (STVEP) Technical key competencies for tech-voc. secondary schools.
 Nakayama, J. (2005). Gender and vocational education and training, A paper presented during the 6th International Training Program at TESDA Women's Center.
 Syjuco, A. B. (2013). Programs: TESDA System. Retrieved on Jan 18, 2013. <http://www.tesda.gov.ph/programs1/tesdsys.asp>
 TESDA Circular No. 21 s. (2006). General Guidelines on the Implementation of Assessment and Certification Program under the Philippine TVET Qualification and Certification System (PTQCS).
 TESDA Circular No. 14 s. (2005). Guidelines in the Implementation of the Philippine TVET Qualification and Certification System.
 Technical Education and Skills Development Authority. (2005). Gender and Development in TVET. A paper presented during the 6th International Training Program at TESDA Women Center
 Technical Education and Skills Development Authority. (1998). Installing a Quality-Assured Technical Education and Skills Development (TESDA) System. 1998 TESDA Transition Report.
 Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA). Philippine TVET Qualification and Certification System: Assessor's Guide
 TESDA Women's Center and Japan International Cooperation Agency. (2006). GAD-Based Entrepreneurship Development in TVET: A Study on the Evaluation of the International Training Program and Third Country Program 2002-2005.
 Technical Education and Skills Development Authority. (2006). Ladderized Education Program
 Technical Education and Skills Development Authority. (2006). TVET Outlook.
 Technical Education and Skills Development Authority. (2006). 2nd Cycle National Technical Education and Skills Development Plan 2004-2009.
 Technical Education and Skills Development Authority. (2005). Gender and Development in TVET, A paper presented during the 6th International Training Program at TESDA Women Center
 Technical Education and Skills Development Authority. (1998). Installing a Quality-Assured Technical Education and Skills Development (TESDA) System. 1998 TESDA Transition Report.

- Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA). Registry of Workers Assessed and Certified: 2000-2005
- Valles, Milagros C. Ed. D (2010). An Approach Used in Strengthening the Technical and Vocational Education Program (STVEP), DepEd, Philippines” TESDA Board Resolution No. 2005-18, (2006). Approving the Provisional Assessment Fees By Qualification.
- TESDA Board Resolution No. 2003-05 (2003). Adoption of the Philippine TVET Qualifications Framework, dated March 13.
- TESDA Board Resolution No. 1998-01,(1998). Installing a Quality-Assured TESD System, dated January 23,
- TESDA Circular No. 21 s. (2006). General Guidelines on the Implementation of Assessment and Certification Program under the Philippine TVET Qualification and Certification System (PIQCS), 2006
- TESDA Circular No. 14 s. (2005). Guidelines in the Implementation of the Philippine TVET Qualification and Certification System.
- Declaration of Policy. Republic Act. No. 7796 (1995). Technical Education and Skills Development Act of 1994 (with Implementing Rules and Regulations).
- TESDA Women’s Center and Japan International Cooperation Agency. (2006). GAD-Based Entrepreneurship Development in TVET: A Study on the Evaluation of the International Training Program and Third Country Program 2002-2005.
- Technical Education and Skills Development Authority. (2006). Ladderized Education Program
- Technical Education and Skills Development Authority. (2006). TVET Outlook.
- Technical Education and Skills Development Authority. (2006). 2nd Cycle National Technical Education and Skills Development Plan 2004-2009.
- Technical Education and Skills Development Authority. (2005). Gender and Development in TVET, A paper presented during the *6th International Training Program at TESDA Women Center.*
- Nakayama, J. (2005). Gender and Vocational Education and Training, A paper presented during the *6th International Training Program at TESDA Women’s Center.*
- Technical Education and Skills Development Authority. (1998). Installing a Quality-Assured Technical Education and Skills Development (TESDA) System. 1998 TESDA Transition Report.
- Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA). Registry of Workers Assessed and Certified: 2000-2005.
- Valles, Milagros C. Ed. D (2010). An Approach Used in Strengthening the Technical and Vocational Education Program (STVEP), DepEd, Philippines.